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Ethnicity and Voting Behavior in Nigeria's Fourth Republic: an Appraisal

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Abstract: The paper observed that voting behaviors of individuals in elections are influenced by some factors such as issues, political party identification, ethnic cleavage, personality of the contestants, and social class of the contestants. In Nigerian context, the work tried to unravel the one that took precedence during the elections in the Fourth Republic. As a result, the study is designed to interrogate the influence of ethnicity on the voting behavior of Nigerians in the period under investigation. We gathered our data from secondary source through Documentary method and analyzed same with Content Analysis. Theoretically, the study utilised Political Economy as the theoretical framework of analysis. The theory informed among others that the propelling force of human actions in our terrestrial existence is the provision of human's economic needs. From the study, we found that many factors, including ethnicity contributed to the winnings of elections in the Fourth Republic. However, we suggested that the electorate should focus more on the personality of the contestant, by voting based on the ability of the contestants. This will be the best way to select a development-driven leader who can practically engage on even dispensation of dividends of democracy to the people in the polity.

Keywords: Elections, Ethnicity, First Republic, Political Parties, Voting Behavior

INTRODUCTION

Inherently, man was created among other things to discern and make varied preferences on issues of his concern. These different choices of humans may subtly or largely be influenced by factors among others, body constitution or personal preferences. This is essentially, the reasons we revere the maxim, which maintains that 'what one likes may be what another dislikes'. The same scenario is observed in the modern political terrain where we traversed from direct to indirect democracy. Direct democracy accords the citizens direct participation in decision making while the indirect democracy therefore, implies participation in the selection of their

leaders through election. In the course of the election however, some factors, which include: ethnicity, issues, party identification and social class influenced largely individual choice of voting (Suberu, 2004). Among the enumerated factors affecting voting behaviour as noted by Suberu, our emphasis is focused on the ethnic factor.

Indeed, the seed of ethnicity appears to have been sown in Nigeria with the advent of colonialism, this is so because prior to colonial rule in the country, there was no unified state in Nigeria, what was in existence were mainly kingdoms, chiefdoms and empires. Given the fact that

urbanisation was inchoate at the time, there was neither a common political system nor unifying myth of ancestry around which identity could focus before the colonial rule (Young, 1977).

With the emergence of colonialism, the common political milieu was completely changed. As a result, those ethnic groups which had previously enjoyed their independence were forcefully joined together and given a new name as a political entity, for example, aside the three main ethnic groups, (Hausa, Igbo and Yoruba), about 260 ethnic groups were lumped into a political entity called Nigeria (Oyari, 2005). Worthy of note also is that formation of ethnic unions is also one of the reasons that brought about ethnicity in the country. In anticipation of the end of colonial rule, various ethnic associations were formed. At the eve of independence, most of these ethnic associations were transformed into political parties, for instance, in 1951, the Northern Peoples Congress (NPC) emerged from “Jamiyya Jama Arewa”ie the congress of Northern Nigeria, which was a cultural organization. Also, in 1951, the Action Group (AG) was formed by a cultural organization established in 1945 in London by some Yoruba students known as Egbe Omo Oduduwa,.

Consequent upon the lopsided and ethnic laden formation of political parties from colonial to the third republican elections in the country, we observed some traces of decisive influence of ethnicity. For instance, in 1979 presidential election where five political parties contested, the NPN (National Party of Nigeria), which was a reformation of the NPC and has Alhaji Shehu Shagari as the presidential flag bearer won the election as a result of numerical strength of the northerners. The same scenario replicated itself in the 1983 election, which was truncated by military intervention. By extension, Olaniyi (2017) opined that there was no clear cut differences between the parties of the First Republic and that of the Second Republic apart from the fact that in the Second Republic, the NPN made efforts to involve elites from various parts of the Nigeria, a gesture which actually enhanced the political influence of the party, while remaining parties except National Advance Party (NAP), were ethnically based.

More so, the 1993 presidential elections, which was contested by Tofa and Abiola was annulled

among other reasons that the alleged winner, MKO Abiola was not from the same ethnic group with the military dictator (Babangida). Be that as it may, the paper focused on the interrogation of impact of ethnicity on voting behaviour in Nigeria’s Fourth Republic. For the purpose of brevity, the work is streamlined under the following paradigms: clarifications of ethnicity, Fourth Republic and voting behaviour, theoretical nexus, principles and determinants of voting behaviour, the history of ethnicity and politics in Nigeria, ethnicity and elections in Nigerian political system during the fourth republic, conclusion and prognoses.

The Concept of Ethnicity

Ethnicity as a concept in Social Science diction has attracted scholarly debate in the world of academia over its meaning. Based on this circumstances, it can be conceptualized as a social condition that is related to competition between different ethnic groups (Nnoli (1978). Clarifying further, he conceived ethnic groups as social formations differentiated by the peculiar character of their members manifested especially in their language, culture or both, with language constituting the most essential variable in Africa. For Eteng (2004), ethnic groups, however, are not mandatorily homogeneous in language or culture, rather, it may often subsumes class differences, dialectic, linguistic, occupational and sub-cultural depending on the level of prevailing cultural differentiation and socio-economic development.

In another development, Azeez (2004) construed ethnicity as a feeling of people hood and oneness that has its origin in common aspiration and the remembrance of past experience. Impliedly as rightly deciphered by Eteng as demonstrated above is that ethnicity is driven from the ethnic group, which forms the fundamental of its activation and articulation, which means that it is the manifestation of the group that makes ethnicity possible. According to him however, it (ethnicity) does not exist independent of the group that embodies it.

The Fourth Republic

For a clear understanding of the concept of Fourth Republic in Nigerian political terrain, it is paramount importance to demystify the concept of republic. Hence, a republic can be construed as a

[type of government](#), where a country is recognized as a "public matter", not as a [private property](#) of the ruling class. According to *Arthur (2010)*, the fundamental position of power in a republic is not based on inheritance, rather, a form of government, which the monarch is not the head of state. American diction, the republic is referred to a system of government where elected individuals are allowed to represent the citizens and exercised political powers based on the dictates of the constitution. In other words, facilitates constitutionalism. It guarantees [separation of powers](#) between the elected [head of state](#) and other arms of government, more so, referred to as a constitutional republic and/or [representative democracy](#).

Etymologically, the concept "the republic" was coined in the first instance in Rome C. 500 BC, subsequently however, it changed severally in the meaning. Indeed, republic implies the Latin name 'res publica' which means "a quasi form of democracy" as obtainable in Rome C. 500 BC - C. 27 BC. Interestingly, the Roman Senate who held all of the seats was checked by the institution of the [consulship](#) in the Roman quasi-democracy, the power of the aristocratic class, whose two consul/vice-rulers were elected annually by the free citizens or [plebes](#) of Rome. The definition of the word in ancient Roman differs from the modern use of the word, where the leadership is not restricted to the ruling class (Allen, 2004).

By implication, a republic in Nigerian context ends when there is military intervention through *Coup d'états* or any other means. Historically therefore, after independent constitution of 1960, Nigeria had her First Republic in 1963 where the citizens were allowed to vote and be voted for. This seemingly lofty political development was truncated by 1966 coup and counter coup, which heralded a three year civil war in Nigeria between 1967 and 1970. The Second Republic commenced from 1979 and ended in 1983 when Buhari toppled the government of Alhaji Shehu Shagari, which was subsequently overthrown by Babangida in 1985. The military interregnum held sway from 1983 till 1992 when the United Nations threatened to designate Nigeria as a pariah state. In reaction to this development, the annulled Third Republic was highlighted and demonstrated. Sequel to the annulment of the

elections and the concomitant threat from the United Nations, the military junta decided to step aside and made Shonekan the interim President of the nation. No sooner had he (Shonekan) assumed the position than he relinquished the power to Abacha who died in the year 1998 thereby made way for Abdulsalam to organise and hand over to a civilian government of the Fourth Republic in 1999. In the Fourth Republic, we have had democratic elections in the following years: 2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019 and 2023.

Voting Behavior

In order to conceptualize the phrase, voting behavior, it is vital to unravel the individual terms. Unequivocally, voting, as opined by Bromehead (1964) implies a way and means by which citizens are allowed to make their choice over who will rule them. It is an act of agreeing or agreeing with propositions, or their choices between two or more candidates that contested for offices. It is also, a way of integrating individual choices into a collective decision. On the other hand, Ugwu, (1997) averred that behaviour implies a response of man and or organism towards stimulations from environment. Furthermore, it encapsulates those activities that man and animals engage in, ranging from their emotions, ways of communicating and their actions.

In the view of Bratton (2013), voting behaviour entails a set of individual electoral activities, such as turnout at the polls, electoral campaign participations and selection of, to whom to vote. According to him, the voting Behaviour has expanded recently in the meaning and connotation because it has been taken as a study area in the social science discipline. Invariably, voting Behaviour is not new concept in social science setting, but it is used of recent to demonstrate political phenomena and some areas or types of study, which initially had neither conceived nor regarded as relevant (Zahida & Younis, 2014). They went further to claim that voting behaviour is not just limited to record taking, calculation of statistics of voting, electoral shifts computation and swings but also, involves an analysis of the psychological processes of individuals (emotion, motivations and perceptions) and their relationships to political action as well as the

pattern of institution, like process of communication and their electoral impacts.

Theoretical Nexus

This study is anchored on political economy as the theoretical framework around which the work revolved. The proponents of the theory include: Engels (1975); Lenin, (1975); Marx, (1975); and supported by Ake (1981); Ihonvebere, (1985); Akpuru-Aja, 1998) and some other contributors. The propositions maintained among other things that the actions of an individual or state in the society are absolutely guided by economic reason. Hence, when one understands economic condition of a people, one has gone a long way in understanding the other aspect of their life such as political, religious, cultural and law (Ake, 1981).

Political economy as a theoretical framework is anchored on dialectical materialism, which accords primacy to economic conditions of life in the society. It is hinged on the notion that man is largely propelled by material needs. Hence, labour is the primary essence of our social existence. Therefore, man's economic activity is his fundamental concern concern (Ihonvebere, 1985). Essentially, Akpuru-Aja (1998). Contended that the crux of this position is on how the understanding of economic structure of a society, as defined by the relations between the owners of means of production and the workers in the process of production determines or enhances the understanding of her politics and culture. Also, in Engels (1975) Marx claimed that all the political systems correspond or reflect the type of economic structure; as a result, he placed primacy on production basis (substructure) in understanding of the culture, ideology and politics, of a society (superstructure)

Moreover, from the point of view of economic determinism, we may better believe as follows: (a) the nature of the internal relations; (b) how the society manages, reproduces and organizes, and itself; (c) the causes of conflicts, contradictions or tensions in a given society and (d) the directions or bearing of change in the society (Akpuru-Aja, 1998). In corroboration, Marx, (1975) intoned that the major cause of class antagonism or tension in the society is largely determined by economic factors. If one is abreast with the economic structure of a given society, the relations between the owners of means of production and the worker

in the production process, it is easier to ascertain its nature of culture, ideological disposition, national security and politics. On the other hand, economic activities directly influences other structures of the superstructure of society

By a way of application, economic need is the most decisive need of man as noted earlier; the same scenario equally applies to economic activities (production). Essentially, production is social in nature which implies that it requires a combination of human intellectual and physical powers. By implication, it is in the rational bid of men to realize the fundamental need of man, through social relations in production process that made them to strategize by forming groups. The groups include: age group, class group, work group, professional group, ethnic group etc. Indeed, these groups are consciously formed for the primary purpose of promotion and protection of economic interest of the members. Specifically, ethnicity, which is sentimental attachment to ones ethnic group shares the same value and orientation with the enumerated groups. To begin with, everybody wants to be at decision-making circle in the society which can only be possible in a direct democracy, reasons being among others that no one makes decision against his interest (Ogban, 2005).

By extension, population surge in the modern society has made a jest of direct democracy; hence the obtainable political system is indirect democracy where a few people are elected to make decisions for the populace. This development does not in any way debunk the fundamental truth clearly stated by Ogban in his submission above. It is on this conviction that the voting behaviour of the electorate in the Nigerian Fourth Republic, which is more or less contributed to mediocrity and bad governance in the country influenced by the ethnicity. Be that as it may, ethnic groups are recognized and welcomed in the society but the ethnicity, which is tilting towards fundamentalism should be discouraged because it ferments discord, rancor, hatred and all sort of disintegration, which appears to be aberration to a multiethnic nation like Nigeria. Therefore, the more we shun those negative aspect of ethnic considerations, the more we consider other factors that influence voting behaviour, the more we vote qualified and

credible persons into governance and the less we have mediocre in position of authority.

Principles and Determinants of Voting Behaviour

Dwelling in British environment, Bagehot (1980) stated that the British are clearly different to authority and are prone to differentiate their decision making to those that claimed to be born to rule, that is those that believed to know better than others, hence, the motivation of conservative party, which during the 19th century, was mainly staffed from the ranks of the wealthy, the privileged and landed gentry. The traditional authority was represented by the conservative. Following the analysis, he maintained that party image rather than specific policy is the main factor that affects voting behavior in the society.

In a larger dimension, according to Dudley (1982) three theories were identified to explain reasons that are responsible for the way people vote in elections. The theories involve: a) Cue Theory, b) Rational Choice Theory and c) Social Group Theory. By extension, Cue Theory insisted that party ideological position, programs and electioneering platforms are really the cues that help to prompt the voters to vote in a particular way. Also, the Rational Choice Theory construed the voters as simply as a consumer that has resources to expand, the resources in this instance implies his vote. Like every rational consumer, the voters have a defined function he seeks to maximize; hence, he expands his resources by voting for the party he agreed that would best maximize this defined function. The aim could be status position/some special interests or the other or power. However, the Social Group Theory believes that people are opened to vote in a particular way because of the social group they belong.

More so, Suberu (1991) articulated four broad factors such as class, ethnicity, issue, and party identification as the determinants of voting behaviour in the society. Explaining further, he

stated that issues are relatively insignificant in determining voting of the people, that the electorates are largely not influenced by substantive policies. This is so according to him that parties do not present to the electorate their issue preferences. On the area of the party identification, he insisted that many of the electorates vote for the same party consistently over time with newer voters inheriting party loyalties from their families. More so, in the case of ethnicity, he contended that nothing is as vital to the voters of ethnic group as the involvement of a member of the ethnic group to vie for a post in an election. Essentially, inactive electorate can be enthusiastic to vote when a member of his ethnic group is contesting. Hence, majority of the politicians have noticed that stimulating ethnic emotions and sentiments is an efficient approach for mobilizing for supports and loyalty in an election. Lastly, class, which can be defined with education, income or occupation, is a necessary factor that influences voters because the working class group tends to align with Labour Party politically whereas the upper class and the middle class usually align politically with the Conservative Party.

Furthermore, Okolie (2004) enumerated the undrlisted factors as the determinants of voting behaviour in the society: campaign slogan, ethnicity, material consideration, party manifesto, party organization, personality of the contestants, propaganda and religion. To expatiate further, he stated that one fundamental point behind all voting is to make decisions on issues at stake. Therefore, the focus of the decisions is influenced by the mentioned factors above, which direct the voting behavior of the electorate. Description of factors affecting the electorates in the voting process is inexhaustible in the existing literature. Therefore, we shall use table 1 below to demonstrate the factors and their description for clearer understanding.

Table 1: Descriptions of Factors Influencing Voting Behaviour

SN	FACTORS	DESCRIPTIONS
1	Campaign Slogan and Propaganda	This is a situation where the rational electorate considers the campaign slogan and propaganda of political party during voting.
2	Class	Here, the electorate considers class of the members of the political party whether they are the working class, middle class or the bourgeois class.
3	Ethnicity	Under ethnicity, membership of one's ethnic group is given preference by the voters

		during an election.
4	Ideology	Political party ideology, whether socialism or capitalism is considered by the electorates while casting their votes.
5	Issue	At this, the electorates consider the substantive policy presented to them by the party while voting for any candidate.
6	Material consideration	Here, the voters specifically calculate financial benefits accruing from a particular contestant before voting.
7	Party identification	This is where the voters vote in an electorate because the person belongs to his political party.
8	Party organization and manifesto	This is a situation where some rational voters put into consideration the manifesto of a political i.e. what it intends to do when elected into office.
9	Personality of the contestants	On this, some people are propelled to support a candidate because of what the person is up to i.e. what the person can do.
10	Religion	Here the electorate accept or reject a particular contestant because he belongs to one religion or the other e.g. Christianity or Muslim

Source: Improvised by the author

The table above demonstrated 10 factors that influence electorate in the process of making choices during elections. The factors however involve the following: Campaign slogan and propaganda, Class, Ethnicity, Ideology, Issue, Party identification, Party organization and manifesto, Personality of the contestants and Religion. The instances of the factors are clearly illustrated on the table for easy comprehension.

History of Ethnicity and Politics in Nigeria

Ethnicity has been a common feature of party politics in Nigerian democracy. It appears to be factual that the national identity of Nigeria is being at odds with the appeal of more exclusive ethnic identity since the colonial period. For instance, before Nigerian independence in 1960, party formation and party politics have assumed an ethnic dimension, even when it transverse into the first republic in 1963. In the political context, as conceived by Sklar, (1963) Egbe Omo Oduduwa, which was a cultural association of the Yoruba educated elite metamorphosed to the Action Group; the Ibo state union which was closely allied with NCNC played a vital role in the internal affairs of the party, whereas the Fulani aristocracy founded NPC during the period. In all, a local political party was often indistinguishable from the cultural association in the smaller ethnic groups,

Most significantly, Azeez (2009) contended that the division of the country by the Richards constitution of 1946 into three regions for easy administration brought about and or invoked the strong regional sentiments. The implication of this action was that the main political parties in Nigeria by 1953 such as - AG, NCNC, and NPC, were linked with the three main ethnic groups of regions in the country – Eastern, Northern and Western. To further clarify the three ethnic attachments, the leaderships of the parties were structured as follows: the NPC of the North was led by Sir Ahmadu Bello, Sardauna of Sokoto; the ace for the Igbos NCNC, was held by Dr. Nnamdi Azikwe, whereas the AG in the Yoruba West was controlled by Chief Obafemi Awolowo, each representing his ethnic divides. Be that as it may, it is however, the absence of a purposeful cross-national political party, strong, visionary, and well-organized with a national outlook, as well as organizational depth and durable popular support for democratic effectiveness and legitimacy among others that made the first republic to the collapse.

More so, he further contended that the constitution of 1979, which brought about the second republic made policies were geared towards giving Nigerian political parties a national outlook, in both the structure and their operations. In spite of the efforts put in place during the second republic, the party formation and politics in the country followed the ethnic dimension as observed in their

formation and operations in the first republic. For instance, after the death of the NPC leader, Ahmadu Bello, the newly registered political parties towed the ethnic lines of the former. That is the more reason the leadership of AG which reincarnated to UPN, whereas the control of NPP - an affiliate of the old NCNC was retained by Nnamdi Azikwe. The GNPP and PRP, that later became NAP as the minority parties, equally adopted the ethnic coloration and affiliations of the first republic. However, the third republic experienced the worst party politics, when the military took over. Later, during the military era, General Babangida and General Abacha defined rules for the formation of political parties. That was what paved way for the registration of only two political parties such as Social Democratic Party (SDP) and National Republican Convention (NRC) by the government of General Babangida. With all intent and purpose, the formation of the two parties was in a particular interest of the self-acclaimed President. This can be attested to through the annulment of the generally agreed as the freest and fairest election of June 12, 1993. However, ethnic sentiments were decipherable in the compositions and membership of the two registered political parties. Where SDP was dominated by the southerners, the NRC favored the Hausa/Fulani north. In another development, the five political parties that were registered during the Abacha regime, such as 1) United Nigeria Congress Party (UNCP), 2) Grassroots Democratic Movement (GDM), 3) Democratic Party of Nigeria (DPN), 4) National Centre Party of Nigeria (NCPN) and 5) Congress for National Consensus (CNC), were purposely established to adopt General Abacha as their consensus presidential candidate, a ploy which was targeted at transforming from the military to civilian president as done in Burkina Faso by his friend, Blaise Campaore among others. The aims and composition of the parties made them to be referred by Chief Bola Ige as “five fingers of a leprous hand” (Azeez, 2009). In the view of Nwankwo (2001) the praetorian origin of the parties was the reasons they were referred as such. In demonstrating the dependent

postures of the parties, he maintained that these parties had no identity of their own, no mind of their own, and no authority of their own. Although, General Abacha’s sudden death on June 8, 1998 ended the self-succession transition programme, thereby paved way for the emergence of the Fourth Republic, which was piloted by General Abdulsalam Abubakar through a brief transition programme. This opened the gate for political activities that is usually characterized by alignment and realignments as well as merger. Sequel to the political gimmicks and pressures, out of 26 political associations that sought for registrations, provisional registration was granted to only nine parties. Finally, only three political parties out of the nine that were granted provisional registration were fully registered after the Local Government elections. Such registered parties included: the Alliance for Democracy (AD), the All People’s Party (APP) later known as All Nigerian Peoples Party (ANPP) and the Peoples Democratic Party (PDP). After the election and emergence of Chief Olusegun Obasanjo emerging as the executive president of the federation, by 29th May 1999, Azeez, (2009) confirmed that the ethnic coloration of the past experiments still manifested in the present political dispensation.

Buttressing the above position, he narrated that ANPP was considered as a party prominently dominated by the Hausa/Fulani, and that the AD succeeded Chief Obafemi Awolowo’s Action Group and Unity Party of Nigeria, thereby dominated the six states of Yoruba extraction viz: Ekiti, Lagos, Ogun, Ondo, Osun and Oyo, until they lost all the states in 2003 except Lagos. Recently however, the ruling PDP appears to have shifted a bit from the usual ethno-religious dominated party politics of the past with their membership and formation traversing the whole Nigeria. However, decipherable from the historical past is that our colonial master sowed the seed of ethnic political party in the country, a legacy that held sway during and after colonialism till the Third Republic. Empirically, table 2 below demonstrates the ethnic based political parties in the country before the Fourth Republic.

Table 2: Political Parties in Nigeria, Year of Formation, Ethnic Based and Leaders before the Fourth Republic

S/N	Political parties	Years	Ethnic Dominance	Period	Leaders
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1	NNDP	1923	Yoruba	Colonial era	Herbert Macaulay
2	NYM	1936	National	Colonial era	Eyo Ita
3	NCNC	1944	Igbo	Colonial era	Herbert Macaulay
4	AG	1951	Yoruba	First Republic	Obafemi Awolowo
5	NPC	1951	Hausa	First Republic	Sarduana of Sokoto
6	UMBC	1955	South-South	First Republic	Joseph Tarka
7	New NNDP	1964	Yoruba	First Republic	S. Akintola
8	NPN	1977	Hausa	Second Republic	Alhaji Shehu Shagari
9	NPP	1978	Igbo	Second Republic	Dr. NnamdiAzikiwe
10	UPN	1978	Yoruba	Second Republic	Obafemi Awolowo
11	GNPP	1978	Hausa	Second Republic	Alhaji Waziri Ibrahim
12	NAP	1978	Yoruba	Second Republic	Tunji Braithwaite
13	PRP	1979	Hausa	Second Republic	Malam Aminu Kano
14	NRC	1992	National	Third Republic	Bashir Othman Tofa
15	SDP	1992	National	Third Republic	MKO Abiola

Source: Compiled by the Author from Nnabuihe, etal (2014) & Okonkwo etal (2016)

The table above demonstrates the names of political parties that existed in the country, starting from colonial period till the Third Republic, their years of establishments, ethnic dominance, the republic and one of the leaders/flag bearers of the parties. Extrapolations therein are that during the colonial era, the parties existed were ethnic based except NYM that had a national outlook. The four political parties that participated in the elections in the First Republic then were ethnically based. Second Republic however recorded the same ethnic character where the six parties that contested in the 1979 and 1983 elections were ethnic dominated parties. It was in the Third Republic that the government in its bid to discourage the idea of sectional party politics established two centrally controlled parties (NRC and SDP). As a result, they appeared national in all ramifications only that the action on the part of government was an aberration to principles of democracy.

Ethnicity and Voting Pattern in Elections during the Fourth Republic

The inevitability of elections and the concomitant voting in democratic setting has attracted the

interest of scholars in social science in general and Political Science in particular to unravel the determinants of voting patterns of the electorate. Hence, scholars have delved into the phenomenon which necessitated much literature on the voters and their behavior, which is simply conceived as voting behaviour. Voting behavior according to Yakubu and Ali, (2017) is one of the basic forms of political behavior, which is always analyzed in relationship with elections. In the study of Cutright and Rossi, (1958), they argued that the outcome of election is a bundle of many factors, which involve a) the activities of the competing party organizations, b) the characteristic of the candidate, c) the informal groups, d) the influence the mass media, e) the communications processes and f) the social and psychological characteristics of the voters.

More so, Campell et al. (1960) suggested that ethnicity should not be discarded as a factor affecting the voter's choice of candidacy but the way it is perceived should be redefined. This therefore, corroborates the assertion about voting according to Horowitz (1985) where he demonstrated that elections are nothing more than ethnic agreement. In corroboration to the influential nature of ethnicity in the choice of the candidate in election by the electorate, they

claimed that in the previous years, the study of ethnicity and racial factors on voting behaviour dominated studies of other issues. In line with the above view, Ihonvbere and Shaw (1998), contended that electoral competition in Nigeria is hard to be separated from ethnicity, hence, invocation of ethnic emotions become part of the political system.

Materialistically, Aluko, (2002) intoned that in the political atmosphere of Nigeria, no matter the popularity one thought he is, his desire to render selfless service, honour, integrity, reputation and records, if he do not have money, he is joking. Hence, he insisted that elective positions are always occupied by the wealthy in the country. According to Ukiwo (2004), since the independence of Nigeria in 1960, ethnicity majorly influenced who occupies what position Nigerian politics. From his study also Brantan (2004) resolved that ethnicity and race had large influence on voting behavior of the citizen. Therefore, voters can vote candidate from their own ethnic group or race on the belief that the candidate has their political views. Extending further, Blais (2005) contended that, as much as social characteristics like class has become less significant over time, it is impossible to understand recent Canadian elections without looking at religion and ethnicity as basic determinants of voting behavior of the electorate.

Furthermore, Erdmann (2007) observed that ethnicity makes available the fundamental social link for voting in the countries of Africa. More so, Lindberg and Morrison (2008) observed that ethnic and clientelistic propelled voting are insignificant features of the voting behavior in Ghana. In corroboration with the above submissions of Aluko and Brantan, Orji (2009) noted that in Nigeria, the politics of give and take is very much determinant of who emerges a winner in any election. Expatriating further, he averred that politicians always indulge in the habit of giving out money during elections in Nigeria for the purpose of securing the votes of the electorates and this habit has been seen as normal to the extent that, no matter the level of suitability and qualification a candidate, if the person cannot give out money, the person might likely lose the elections.

Pessimistically, Tenuche (2009) observed that in Nigeria, voting behaviour is full of abusive language and incineration by both the voters and the contestants. Illustrating further, He presented the case the election of President Olusegun Obasanjo in 2007, where he stated that 'elections are wars that must be won by all means possible'. This unveiled further that, for an election to be won by incumbent, he should not rely on powers of the voters, rather by the use of subjugation and coercive methods which include: political assassination, election rigging and even political thuggery. The voters also imbibed the attitude and it became a kind of political behavior of the electorate during the process of election. Hence, shaping the voting pattern is such in a way that electorates are often forced to vote for a particular contestant or to shun voting for it will not count.

Historically, Metumara (2010) averred that political behaviour and voting pattern in Nigeria is affected by an amalgam of rival ethnic groups that were set against each other in a fierce rivalry in a struggle for power and competition for control of scarce resources and this has been visible in the political processes. This sometimes even threatens the corporate existence of the country. This scenario has been rooted since colonial era and any political arrangement during colonial administration that is convincing failed. It takes the intervention of military to avoid the full eruption of ethno-religious conflict into national war. But, with the resurgence of democracy in 1999 exploded the politics of ethno-religion where voting pattern is anchored around ethnic and religion choice of candidate. One other main issue that determines political behaviour and affects voting pattern in Nigeria is religion. Nigeria is mainly divided among Muslim/Christian dichotomy.

In a different perspective, Nigerians according to Onapajo (2012) are more loyal to religion than the state. This is carefully deciphered from the trend of what he called "Religiosity of politics" where the outcome of election is determined by religious affinity in a democratic setting. By implication, voting behaviour of the voters is affected by this, and one cannot imagine discarding the influence of religion in elections in Nigerian. Besides religion and ethnicity, other factors that influence voting behaviour of the electorates in Nigeria

include: manipulation, rigging, political violence and prebendalism.

Precisely, Olayode (2015) noted that the general elections are largely showcased with predominance of ethnic emotions as the influential factor of voting behaviour of the electorate in Nigeria. For him, from the presidential election, gubernatorial, national and state house assemblies, the aspirants were basically selected on the ground of ethnic group. The President and Vice President elect in the presidential election received 90% of their votes on the ground of ethnic group. Also, the current President received much votes from his ethnic lineage. This has been the norms in political arena of Nigeria, where votes are cast based on ethnic cleavage and emotions by each particular group in the country where their contestants emerge irrespective of whether he will he will loss or win through their votes.

Indeed, Wogu et al (2015) agreed that elections and democracy in Nigeria are influenced by poor institutionalization of democratic culture and values. In their views, tribalism and inter-ethnic competition are the great weakness, which leads to democratic instability in the country. Also, they averred that the constitutional democracy in Nigeria is so fragile because it was imported. For example, the announcement of the victory of the Northern Presidential candidate in the 1984 brought about the rioting in the Southwest and Southeast, which culminated in the end of the Second Republic. As a result, the military took

over immediately. This demonstrated the political culture of the electorates in Nigeria on the belief that only a contestant of their ethnic group can emerge as a winner of any election.

Osayi (2015) opined that Godfatherism is the major factor in determining who will get the platform of contest among political parties and to a larger extent, the emergence of the winner in the general election. Some powerful cabals constituted themselves into a gangster that influence who should be elected. They sponsor these godsons and manipulate the electoral process to ensure he emerges by hook or crook means. In some other time, politics of money influence voters behaviour. Nevertheless, Ademowagun (2015) opined that some people assume that Nigerians only vote on the ground of religion and ethnicity, though, the voting pattern of the electorate is not one-directional. Hence, he delineated the following six types of voters as being prevalent in Nigeria political milieu: a) the cynics, b) The devotees, c) The ethicists, d) The partisans, e) The revolutionist and f) The sophisticated. Indeed, we have an avalanche of postulations of scholars on the propelling force of ethnicity on voting behaviour especially in the Fourth Republic. For clarity sake, table three below empirically displayed the elections in the Fourth Republic, the years, ethnic groups, political parties of the winners and the factors that facilitated the winning (voter's choice).

Table 3: Factors that Facilitated the Winning of Elections in the Fourth Republic

S/N	Years	Winners	Ethnic Groups	Parties	Factors
1	1999	Olusegun Obasanjo	Yoruba	PDP	Personality
2	2003	Olusegun Obasanjo	Yoruba	PDP	Party Affiliation
3	2007	Umaru Musa Yar' Adua	Hausa	PDP	Ethnicity/Party affiliation
4	2011	Goodluck Ebele Jonathan	South-South	PDP	Party affiliation
5	2015	Muhammadu Buhari	Hausa	APC	Ethnicity

6	2019	Muhammadu Buhari	Hausa	APC	Ethnicity/Party Affiliation
7	2023	Bola Tinubu	Yoruba	APC	Party Affiliation

Source: improvised and compiled by the author

Decipherable from the table above is that the first election conducted in the Fourth Republic was in the year 1999. The election was won by Olusegun Obasanjo of PDP and from Yoruba extraction. The winning was majorly influenced by his personality as calculated by the way he peacefully handed over powers to a civilian government in the Second Republic of 1979. By 2003 election, the PDP has gained popularity and unmatched influence in the political terrain of the country; therefore, he won the election based on party affiliation. In 2007 however, the popularity of PDP appeared to be waning but was immediately fortified by ethnic sentiments. Hence, Yar'Adua's winning was majorly motivated by ethnicity and party affiliation. During the 2011 elections, the lapses of PDP were tightened up for Jonathan to maintain the stage provided to him by what was called "child of necessity" as a result, Goodluck Jonathan won the 2011 election based on party affiliation. Subsequently, in 2015 the Hausas mobilised their numerical strength and dragged powers to the north through their support of Muhammadu Buhari under the auspices of APC in 2015 which was merger of opposition parties. In 2019 also, Buhari won ethnic sentiment of the North and the influence of the APC as the ruling party. Finally, the influence of APC transcended to 2023, which necessitated the winning of Bola Tinubu.

Conclusion

Individual preference of candidature of a particular contestant in an election is influenced by some factors which include among others, ethnicity, party affiliation, personality of the contestant, issue, material consideration etc. Indeed, the chapter interrogated the impact of ethnicity in the voting behaviour of the electorates in the Fourth Republic. Discernible there from is that ethnicity was bequeathed to Nigeria by her colonial masters through their principle of amalgamation of different ethnic divides and subsequently adoption of "divide and rule" for administrative convenience where the indirect rule achieved unprecedented success in the north, west

partial success while in the east, it recorded a monumental failure. In the eve of independence and the subsequent First Republic, the nationalists aligned themselves in seemingly ratified ethnic sentimentalism to muster the political muscle to depose the colonial government and hold sway a control of the anticipated republic. As a result, Nigerian political parties during colonial era were metamorphosed from cultural/ethnic organizations. A similar scenario was experienced in the post colonial period. The political parties that were established during the first, second and third republics were mainly ethnic based. With the deeply inculcation of ethnic sentiment in Nigerian political terrain, the aborted Third Republic which imposed two political parties on the citizens could not change the ethnic consternation in Nigerian politics. Therefore, in the Fourth Republic where we have had seven consecutive elections, it is observed that ethnicity played significant roles but was not the major determinant. However, other factors such as personality of the contestant and party affiliation were considered by the electorate during their voting. However, ethnicity is still a factor influencing voter's behaviour in Nigerian but the winners in the Fourth Republican elections were emerged based on other factors.

Prognoses

Based on the findings under the conclusion, the chapter does not in any way kick against ethnic group because there are some adages that state that "who wears shoes knows where it pinches him" and "he who is close to somebody perceives the odour of his teeth". These imply that a closer person and/or one whom you share a common tie with (ethnic) can know your needs more than external person. Inversely, holding the above idea tenaciously in political environment like Nigeria where we have multi-ethnic group is counterproductive because it breeds unmitigated division and unhealthy struggle for power. However, we suggest the following as ways forward:

1. The electorate should in as much as they remember their ethnic origin, focus more on

the integrity of the candidates in the election. This is the ideal guiding principle for voting because voting a candidate for either as a result of ethnicity or party affiliation will definitely cloud the views and visions of the prospective leaders.

2. The political office holder should as a matter of necessity, be guided by the principles of equity while dishing out projects to the masses. If the leaders consider the welfare of all the citizens not minding the ethnic origin and political party affiliation, the country shall achieve even development in the near future.

Therefore, if the electorates are influenced by the personality of the candidates for election while voting as being practiced in the developed world, it will go a long way in bringing socio-economic and political development to Nigeria. It will equally sanitize the seemingly atavistic political sentiments where our politicians misconstrue politics as a 'do or die affair'.

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